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Stress-driven photo-reconfiguration of surface microstructures via vectorial field-guided lithography

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Abstract

Pattern formation driven by mechanical stress plays a fundamental role in shaping structural organization in both natural and human-made systems. Using light as a vectorial stimulus may offer a powerful route to control stress-induced pattern formation in materials. However, achieving localized, programmable, and predictable control of individual microstructures via structured polarization fields has remained a major challenge. Here, we introduce vectorial field-guided lithography, a novel approach that leverages fully structured polarization fields as lithographic tools to enable the stress-driven reconfiguration of pre-patterned azopolymer microstructures with an unprecedented degree of flexibility, complexity, and diversity. By building on the Viscoplastic PhotoAlignment model, which describes the azopolymer deformation as a stress response to structured light, we quantitatively demonstrate and predict complex surface architectures generated by programmable light-induced stress pathways using a digital polarization rotator implemented via a spatial light modulator. We model and experimentally achieve single-step formation of anisotropic, bent, and chiral microstructures from a single pre-patterned geometry. Our results reveal an exceptional control over local microstructure morphology and establish, for the first time, a comprehensive theoretical framework capable of quantitatively designing and fabricating target morphologies on azopolymers. This work moves beyond conventional intensity-based photopatterning and demonstrates that the full vectorial nature of light can dictate the mechanical reshaping of functional polymer surfaces, providing a new platform for the programmable design of complex microarchitectures with applications in photonics, microfluidics, and biology.

Introduction

Stress-driven pattern formation is a fundamental mechanism that governs the emergence of complex structures across spatial and temporal scales in both natural and engineered systems. On Earth's surface, tectonic stress sculpts mountains and fault lines¹. In living organisms, differential growth induces mechanical instabilities, leading to the characteristic folds of the human brain², the wrinkling of the skin³, and the morphological features in plant leaves⁴. Even at the

microscopic level, bacterial colonies self-organize into complex morphologies under the influence of mechanical stress⁵. Despite their diverse origins, these systems share a common underlying principle. When internal stress accumulates, the system undergoes morphological reorganization to minimize free energy, often through symmetry breaking, giving rise to structured topographies. Inspired by this universal process, the engineering of controlled stress-driven deformations has emerged as a powerful strategy to design functional surfaces. Examples include tunable wrinkling in soft materials⁶, origami-inspired folding⁷, and buckling of stretchable materials⁸.

All of these examples leverage the relationship between a triggering external action and the stress generated within the material, with this interaction guiding the material into forming structures. Typically, these systems

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harness the stress induced by external stimuli such as temperature, humidity, or mechanical load^{9,10}. Light, which allows remote, non-contact control with high spatial and temporal accuracy, offers distinct advantages among the other stimuli^{11–13}. More importantly, light inherently carries vectorial information through its polarization state. This degree of freedom remains largely untapped for conventional stress-driven surface structuring and light-based photopatterning processes, such as standard optical lithography.

Amorphous azobenzene-containing polymers (referred to as azopolymers), with their unique light-induced anisotropic stress-driven deformation, offer a route to bridge this gap and harness the vectorial nature of light for surface patterning^{14–16}. Key elements for this process are the photochemical properties of the azobenzene chromophores embedded in the hosting polymeric material matrix. Following cyclic *trans-cis* photoisomerization with UV/visible light, the azobenzene molecules reorient perpendicular to the direction of the local light polarization^{14,15}, transferring their alignment to the polymer to which they are attached through either covalent^{17,18} or supramolecular interactions^{19,20}. The mechanical stress resulting from the photoalignment is relieved by directional plastic deformation of the material in the irradiated area^{18,21}. When the azopolymer is prepared as a thin film, this light-induced phenomenon directly produces relief patterns on the free surface of the film. The morphology of such reliefs reflects the local geometry of the incident vectorial light field, showing a dependence on both the spatial intensity distribution^{22–24} and its local polarization state^{25–27}. Empirical and phenomenological exploitation of the vectorial nature of the light-induced surface deformation of azopolymers has been used to fabricate a wide range of different surface relief architectures. Interestingly, complex anisotropic microstructures, with tailored morphology even in three dimensions, can also be obtained when the intensity or the polarization of the incident light is used to reconfigure the geometry of already pre-patterned surfaces. Complex isometric²⁸, and strongly unidirectional^{29–31} and bidirectional^{32–34} anisometric architectures have been achieved from pristine arrays of azopolymer micropillars in this scheme.

The modeling of azopolymer photopatterning processes has been a long-standing challenge due to the complex interplay between light parameters and material response¹⁵. However, a recent theoretical framework, the Viscoplastic PhotoAlignment (VPA) model, has been proposed to describe the process as a unique stress-driven vectorial phenomenon initiated by the light. This picture could ultimately bridge the existing gap between the nanoscopic photomechanics of azobenzene molecules and the resulting macroscopic surface relief geometries¹⁸. Beyond rationalizing the complex multiscale

photoinduced dynamics in these materials, the relevance of this model lies in the possibility of finally having predictive and inverse design capabilities for the surface reliefs on azomaterials. In addition, extending and validating the model to the general case of irradiation with structured vectorial light fields could provide foresight for the design of unconventional illumination schemes and materials for new lithographic processes.

In this work, we demonstrate a new level of stress-driven morphological control based on the programmable photo-reconfiguration of pre-patterned azopolymer surfaces using structured vectorial light fields. Specifically, we analyze the photo-reconfiguration of azopolymer micropillars illuminated by spatially varying polarization patterns, which are generated by a digital polarization rotator implemented via a computer-controlled spatial light modulator^{35,36}. This optical system offers large flexibility in the polarization pattern design, making our configuration a prototype of a more general vectorial field generator able to control the stress-driven morphological deformation of the azopolymers, with an exceptional degree of complexity and diversity. Furthermore, our experimental framework provides an ideal test ground to further validate the VPA model for arbitrary structured light. The combined experimental and theoretical study presented here demonstrates unprecedented quantitative, predictive capabilities on the morphology and the stress-driven deformation dynamics of complex azopolymer microstructures. Our results establish the concept of the vectorial field-guided lithography, summarized in Fig. 1, whereby a rationally designed vectorial light pattern is directly converted into programmable microstructure morphologies via tailored light-induced stress pathways. The presented framework opens up the exploration of vectorial external stimuli as a tool for shaping even diverse material systems, paving the way for applications in different fields such as photonics, microfluidics, and biology.

Results

Stress-driven morphological deformations from linearly polarized light

Before introducing the general framework of the vectorial field-guided lithography, we first rationalize the photomechanical response of azopolymer micropillars to uniform linearly polarized light as a baseline of the stress-driven morphological deformation described by the VPA model. This photo-reconfiguration scenario^{30,34}, schematized in Fig. 2a, has been used to induce either directional small, reversible deformations³⁷ or complete remorphing of azopolymer micropillar arrays³⁸. However, previous studies have been largely limited to empirical observations and phenomenological accounts of polarization-driven deformation, lacking a quantitative, predictive framework.

For our analysis, the azomaterial surface is designed as an array of cylindrical micropillars and placed in the x - y plane. The surface photo-deformation involves illumination with a homogeneous laser beam, which in our scheme is linearly polarized along the x -axis. The polarization direction is indicated by the blue arrow identifying the direction of the electric field (E) in Fig. 2a. A uniform intensity distribution is taken into account here to minimize contributions from intensity gradients, which are known to be an additional relevant mechanism driving surface deformation in azopolymer films^{22,23} and microstructures³⁹. Moreover, the uniform illumination also

ensures that each micropillar within the irradiated region experiences the same photo-deformation dynamics.

Figure 2b shows the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of our fabricated pristine structured surface. For the photo-reconfiguration experiment, a linearly polarized laser beam at a wavelength of 488 nm was used. The beam was sufficiently expanded to ensure spatial uniformity of the intensity in the illuminated area. Details on our azopolymer, the preparation and the geometry of the pre-patterned array, and the optical setup are presented in Materials and methods and in Fig. S1–S3. Figure 2c shows the reconfiguration process of a micropillar

in the array achieved by exposing the surface for 18 minutes to a laser intensity of 0.16 W/cm^2 . According to the expected phenomenology³⁰, the irradiation breaks the symmetry of the initially isotropic cylindrical micropillar, resulting in an elongated microstructure in the direction of the polarization of the incident light beam. The same happens for all the micropillars in the homogeneously illuminated area.

In the VPA model, the amorphous polymer is schematized as a series of rod-like polymer backbone segments, to which the azobenzene chromophores are attached as side chains, preferentially at right angles. The directional photo-deformation of the azopolymer is triggered by the light-

induced reorientation of the azobenzene chromophores into the plane perpendicular to the electric field E . Since the azopolymer is in a glassy state at room temperature, the VPA model assumes a rigid coupling between the azobenzene chromophores and the polymer backbones. This coupling forces the backbones to align along the polarization direction (Fig. 2d)^{18,21}. In this process, the electric field vector E of the homogeneously polarized beam plays the role of a nematic director that breaks the symmetry of the initially isotropic molecular system¹⁵. Importantly, the emergence of orientation anisotropy within the polymer matrix induces mechanical stress; consequently, the alignment of the polymer backbones generates a light-induced stress.

The complete formalism linking the kinetic equations of azobenzene isomerization to the stress induced in the polymer is detailed in the Supplementary Note 1. To emphasize the most relevant aspect of the VPA model, we derived an insightful expression that directly relates the light-induced stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ to the polarization direction $\hat{\mathbf{E}} = \mathbf{E}/|\mathbf{E}|$ of linearly polarized light:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \tau_0(\hat{\mathbf{E}}\hat{\mathbf{E}} - \boldsymbol{\delta}/3) \quad (1)$$

In this relation, τ_0 is the magnitude of the stress, which increases with the light intensity⁴⁰, the dyadic product $\hat{\mathbf{E}}\hat{\mathbf{E}}$ is a tensor that contains the information about the principal axes of stress tensor, and $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ is the unit tensor. This relation was derived assuming an initial isotropic state of the polymer backbones and is valid for the initial stages of irradiation. The main feature emerging from Eq. (1) is that the major principal axis of the stress tensor for linearly polarized light is aligned with the local director $\hat{\mathbf{E}}$, whose uniform spatial distribution is represented by the blue segments in Fig. 2e. In particular, for the linear polarization $\hat{\mathbf{E}} = (1, 0, 0)$ aligned with the x -axis, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ explicitly becomes:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \tau_0 \begin{pmatrix} 2/3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1/3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1/3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

According to Eq. (2) the stress tensor is represented by three principal normal stresses: the tensile component $\tau_E = 2\tau_0/3$ acting along the major principal direction (x -axis here), and the compressive components $\tau_{\perp} = -\tau_0/3$ acting in the two perpendicular minor principal directions (Fig. 2e)⁴¹. Such a light-induced stress tensor leads to the uniaxial elongation of the illuminated azopolymer along the local light polarization direction and to the compression along the orthogonal directions. Following this description, the stress field of a uniform polarization pattern can be illustrated as a single stress pathway (the black arrow in Fig. 2e), corresponding to the major principal direction of the system, along which the polymer deformation mainly occurs.

It is worth noting that the results of the VPA model apply to any polarization state of the irradiated field. In particular, for an elliptically polarized light, relation (1) predicts a general biaxial deformation of the azopolymer micropillar, where two principal stress directions correspond to the axes of the light polarization ellipse^{42,43}.

To model the micropillar photo-deformation in the situation of Fig. 2, we performed finite element simulations using the complete VPA model (Supplementary note 1), where the azopolymer is treated as a viscoplastic material, and the light-induced stress field was

implemented via a custom subroutine in ANSYS software (see Materials and methods). As discussed in detail in a recent review¹⁵, the main physical mechanism underlying the model is the plasticization of glassy azopolymers under light-induced stress (1), whose magnitude τ_0 has been shown to exceed the yield stress τ_{yield} by a large margin. This observation justifies the use of a viscoplastic material model in the present work. Other possible mechanisms, such as pronounced photo softening or a photoinduced solid-to-liquid transition arising from a reduction of the glass transition temperature⁴⁴, can be safely excluded for the class of azopolymers employed in this study.

Figure 2f shows the modeled initial azopolymer microstructure and its morphology at the end of the photo-deformation process. The anisotropic microstructure that results from the VPA model is clearly in excellent agreement with experimental micropillars in Fig. 2c.

To further investigate the agreement beyond just the morphology at the final stages of the reconfiguration process, we analyzed the temporal dynamics of the azopolymer photo-deformation, extracted from the characterization of the microstructure morphology at different exposure times. The micropillar deformation, both in experiments and model, is quantitatively described by measuring the major (L) and the minor (l) axis of the pseudo-elliptical shape of the top surface, respectively. Both parameters were normalized to the diameter (D_0) of the pristine circular micropillar profile before exposure (see also Movie S1 and Fig. S4 for dynamic modeled and experimental evolution, respectively). The comparison, reported in Fig. 2g, demonstrates quantitative agreement at each stage of the deformation process.

Programmable optical field-guided deformations

The analysis conducted above for the uniform linear polarization state allows us to extend the established concept of the uniform stress pathway of the VPA model to the description of deformation induced by vectorial polarization states. We limit our treatment to spatially structured patterns of linear polarization, but the results are generalizable to arbitrary polarization states. Namely, according to Eq. (1), when the polarization field is spatially structured (i.e., $\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r})$), the stress field also becomes spatially varying ($\tau = \tau(r)$). In this condition, at each point \mathbf{r} within the irradiated azopolymer, the local major principal axis of the stress aligns with the direction of the local linear polarization, enabling a spatially controlled deformation ultimately directed by the optical field.

The vectorial dependence of the stress-driven deformation can be easily visualized through the array of azopolymer micropillars, illuminated with discretized structured patterns of linearly polarized light. In this

configuration, each microstructure in the array is deformed according to the local linear polarization direction, acting as a morphological polarization sensor. For our experiments, we used a digital polarization rotator based on a spatial light modulator (SLM) to irradiate the pre-patterned azopolymer micropillar array. This optical system is designed to rotate the azimuth angle φ of a linearly polarized beam and consists of an SLM interposed between two quarter-waveplates whose axes are each oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ with respect to the incident linear polarization (see Materials and methods)^{20,36}. The output polarization angle φ is determined by the phase delay introduced between the two orthogonal components of the circularly polarized light incident on the device, according to the gray level of a computer-generated image displayed on the SLM (see also Fig. S5)^{25,45}. The digital image can be designed to create spatially varying maps $\varphi = \varphi(x, y)$ of linear polarization by assigning an independent gray value to each pixel of the SLM, as schematically shown in Fig. 3a.

For the 256 gray levels addressable to our SLM (8-bit images), the achievable angular resolution in the output polarization angle is $\sim 1.4^\circ$, which allows fine control over the polarization orientation across the beam profile. In our experimental setup (Fig. 3b), the digital polarization rotator was integrated into an optical projection system (see Materials and methods for further details) to initiate the photo-deformation process of the azopolymer micropillar arrays with spatial selectivity (Fig. 3c). Such an optical configuration enables selective, site-specific remorphing of micropillars across the sample with polarization-dependent individual tuning.

Figure 3d–f first demonstrates the ability of this system to replicate the experimental case presented in the previous section for homogeneous micropillar photo-deformation along on-demand directions. For this experiment, we targeted a uniform linear polarization illumination with an azimuth angle $\varphi = +45^\circ$ across the entire field of view of the system (approximately $130 \mu\text{m} \times 78 \mu\text{m}$, see also Materials and methods). To enhance visualization here and in the remainder of this paper, we use a violet-to-red colormap to directly represent the designed polarization maps. The colors encode the polarization angle φ emerging from the digital rotator system for each gray value addressed to the SLM according to the measured calibration curve reported in Fig. S5. Within this representation, the uniform polarization pattern for $\varphi = +45^\circ$ appears as the homogeneous blue color in Fig. 3d.

Figure 3e shows the experimental optical images representing the irradiated homogeneous light pattern, together with a polarimetry characterization confirming the achievement of the targeted polarization state as the output of the digital polarization rotator. It should be

mentioned that, for the sake of improving the visualization, the optical images in Fig. 3 were collected through a CCD camera using an incoherent LED at 477 nm (with full-width-half-maximum of 29 nm) as a light source. In this way we could drastically reduce unwanted interference fringes caused by the coherent 488 nm laser source used in the photo-reconfiguration experiments (see Materials and methods), without affecting the main outcomes of the characterization of the digital polarization rotator system.

As expected from the previous analysis, a homogeneous elongation of all illuminated micropillars in the direction of the linear polarization was obtained in the experiment (Fig. 3f and Table S1), with a measured average orientation angle $\alpha = +43^\circ \pm 5^\circ$, in full agreement with the target design.

We now demonstrate the next level of control enabled by our optical configuration, where spatially varying polarization maps can be designed to individually reshape the micropillars with independently engineered orientation α across the entire field of view. Owing to the square lattice arrangement of the micropillars in our array, the optical field of view can be easily segmented into square regions, each targeting an individual micropillar with a specific linear polarization orientation (see Materials and methods). The polarization map in Fig. 3g was designed as a checkerboard pattern of linearly polarized light oriented at alternating orthogonal azimuth angles of $\varphi_1 = +45^\circ$ and $\varphi_2 = -45^\circ$. Similarly to the previous uniform illumination, the optical images of the irradiated homogeneous light pattern, together with polarimetry characterization confirming the alternating targeted polarization state, are shown in Fig. 3h. In the image of the irradiated field (first image in Fig. 3h), distinct dark lines are visible at the edges of each of the square regions, as expected from the emergence of singularities at positions of sharp polarization variations in the optical wavefield⁴⁶. These field discontinuities provide additional evidence of the system's ability to control vectorial light. However, they do not play a role in this photo-reconfiguration experiment as they are located outside to the targeted azopolymer micropillars.

The irradiation of the checkerboard polarization pattern on the azopolymer array resulted in the stress-driven regular reshaping of the micropillars, with alternating photo-deformation orientations measured from the SEM image (Fig. 3i) of $\alpha_1 = +43^\circ \pm 4^\circ$ and $\alpha_2 = -43^\circ \pm 5^\circ$, in full agreement with the designed polarization map. Additional experimental examples, highlighting the flexibility of the optical system and the peculiar alternating surface patterns achievable through the stress-driven photo-reconfiguration of this square micropillar array and the possibility to achieve progressive linear rotations, are shown in Fig. S6, S7, respectively.

To conclude with this section, it is worth highlighting that the framework proposed here can be further extended to enable coupled modulation of both light intensity and polarization by introducing an additional linear polarizer into the optical setup, as illustrated in Figs. S8, 9. This extension provides the capability to simultaneously control both the pillar elongation direction (polarization) and the deformation strength (intensity) and could represent a first prototype of a full vectorial lithography able to achieve arbitrary complex directional patterns on surfaces.

Stress-driven complex microstructures from vectorial field

We describe now the complex reconfiguration of individual microstructures through locally engineered stress pathways originated by high-resolution structured polarization fields. This demonstrates the concept of maskless,

programmable, and spatially-addressable vectorial lithography in its essential form.

Figure 4a shows the principle underlying the design of this photo-reconfiguration scheme. Due to the high density of addressable pixels in the optical pattern projected onto the azopolymer surface (~ 15 pixels per μm), we can design high-resolution polarization maps that vary spatially across the surface of a single micropillar (diameter of $D_0 = 6.7 \mu\text{m}$ for these experiments, see also Materials and methods). According to the VPA model, each volume element dV of the irradiated azopolymer would experience the effect of the stress field generated by the local polarization state of the light (Fig. 4a), tending to deform along the major principal direction of the maximum tensile component (with the same phenomenology described in Fig. 2). To have distinct directional deformations, adjoining volume elements should deform along

closely varying directions that are only slightly different. This requires that the orientation $\varphi(x, y)$ of the light polarization field, which dictates the major principal stress direction (see also Supplementary note 2 and Fig. S10), varies smoothly across the x-y plane, as shown in Fig. 4a. In this condition, locally curved stress pathways emerge (black lines in Fig. 4b), which lead to complex deformation geometries for the azopolymer microstructures.

According to this description, the polarization map in Fig. 4c was designed by gradually rotating the polarization azimuth φ clockwise from 0 to π along the x-axis of a square segment of $\sim 12 \times 12 \mu\text{m}^2$, while remaining uniform along the y-axis. In the figure, the circular profile of

the pristine pillar and its position relative to the designed polarization map is visualized as a white circle of diameter D_0 . Such a polarization field (see Fig. S11 for the optical characterization) induces an inverted U-shaped stress pathway inside the micropillar volume (Fig. 4d), which consistently guides the deformation of the azopolymer micropillar in the experiment (Fig. 4e, top row). The results of the VPA modeling quantitatively reproduce the observed morphology (Fig. 4e, bottom row) and its temporal dynamics (see also Movie S2). In addition, Fig. 4f shows another square polarization map where the azimuth angle φ is designed to rotate along the x-axis progressively by $\Delta\varphi = +\pi/2$ from the left edge to the center

and then by $\Delta\varphi = -\pi/2$ from the center to the right edge. This design is apparently similar to the previous case, since it has the same initial and final polarization directions. However, it is characterized by a different relative spatial evolution of the azimuth angle, which generates a chiral stress pathway (Fig. 4g) that leads to the final experimental and modeled S-shaped microstructure shown in Fig. 4h (see also Movie S2).

The striking difference observed in the morphologies of the structures Fig. 4e,h demonstrates the critical role of the induced mechanical stress in the azomaterial photo-reconfiguration process, providing clear evidence of the validity of the VPA model in the general case of structured light irradiation. Not only the local polarization state, but also the spatial evolution dynamics of the polarization ultimately define the actual stress pathway. Structured vectorial light fields then become a powerful tool for guiding the morphological reconfiguration of the microstructures.

Importantly, the polarization maps are not limited to unidirectional uniform linear variations, but can have other spatial dependencies, such as angular evolutions, and may also include discontinuities. Due to the circular profile of our particular pristine micropillars, a relevant example is the polarization maps designed with cylindrical symmetry in a polar coordinate system that uses the micropillar center as the origin of the reference system. In this case, the polarization direction φ in the x-y plane depends only on the polar angle θ , while it is uniform along the radial coordinate. Figure 5a shows a first polarization map designed according to the functional dependence $\varphi(\theta) = \varphi_0 + \theta/2$, where $\varphi_0 = \pi/4$ is the polarization azimuth at $\theta = 0$. This polarization map is expected to generate stress pathways with triaxial symmetry (Fig. S10), whose geometry could also be visually represented in a simplified way by connecting the center of the pillar with the positions at the pillar perimeter where the local polarization is parallel to the local surface normal (the black solid arrows in Fig. 5b).

Photo-reconfiguration experiments and VPA modeling in Fig. 5c show the expected “tripetal” anisotropic microstructure resulting from irradiation with the designed structured polarization pattern. Notably, such a design is accompanied by a polarization singularity line in the optical field at $\theta = 3\pi/2$ (see also Fig. S11). However, its role in the photo-reconfiguration dynamics was negligible due to the size of the pristine micropillar, which was significantly larger than the region of zero field intensity within the singularity. It is worth mentioning that in ANSYS the polarization rotation is implemented as a local rotation of the element coordinate systems (see Materials and methods) and does not explicitly account for polarization singularities. Accurate treatment of singularities is ensured through the tailored meshing

strategy. Then, the agreement of the modeled reconfigured microstructure with the experimental one further confirmed the little influence of the optical singularity in this case. By adjusting the rotation angle of the local linear polarization, the number of stress pathways can be further increased (Fig. 5d–f). The polarization map shown in Fig. 5d was designed as $\varphi(\theta) = \varphi_0 + \theta$, in which the local linear polarization undergoes a full 2π rotation along the polar angle θ and $\varphi_0 = 5\pi/4$. This design creates a quadriaxial system of stress pathways (Fig. 5e), resulting in a photo-reconfigured “quadrupetal” anisotropic microstructure in the model (see also Movie S3), as well as in the experiments (Fig. 5f).

Furthermore, Fig. 5g–i demonstrates the extension of the concept to multiaxial stress pathways generated by composing multiple polarization maps. The map in Fig. 5g was designed by segmenting the target area into two rectangular tiles with linearly varying polarization patterns. The upper half of the map features a -2π rotation of linear polarization from the left to the right edge, while the lower half undergoes a linear $-\pi$ rotation. This polarization field generates three curved stress pathways as shown in Fig. 5h, which deform the microstructure into a peculiar “trident-shaped” anisotropic architecture, correctly described by the VPA model (Fig. 5i and Movie S3).

As the last step, we demonstrate that the same stress-driven photo-reconfiguration mechanism driving single pillar deformation can be scaled to the entire array fitting into the optical field of view of the projection system (Fig. 6). Given that surface functionality typically arises from the formation of structured arrays rather than from isolated elements, this approach unlocks the potential for creating large-area, multifunctional surface architectures^{47,48}.

Figure 6a schematizes a square-segmented vector field that is aligned with the array of micropillars. Here, the S-shaped geometry shown in Fig. 4f–h was chosen as the base architecture for local pillar reconfiguration in each segment. The segments were then globally rotated by three different angles with respect to the pillar centers, as visible in the polarization maps in Fig. 6b (left column). After exposure, the resulting surface morphologies in the SEM images show the expected array of complex S-shaped microarchitectures with varying global rotations, clearly demonstrating the ability of our vectorial light fields to tailor the shape of surface arrays into desired, on-demand architectures with complex anisotropy.

Discussion

In this study, we introduce the vectorial field-guided lithography as a new approach for the stress-driven photo-reconfiguration of azopolymer microstructures. By leveraging the core framework of the Viscoplastic Photo

Alignment (VPA) model for the photo-deformation of azopolymers, we demonstrate how structured polarization fields can serve as active and precise tools to control the morphological transformation of azopolymer surfaces. This approach captures the vectorial essence of light and translates it directly into programmable stress pathways that guide the deformation of the microstructures.

Using this approach, we experimentally realize a broad class of complex surface microstructures, having individual or collective anisotropic, bent, and even chiral morphology, through a single-step exposure of a single pre-patterned micropillar array to fully and digitally programmable structured polarization patterns.

Importantly, we validated the VPA model across the full range of structured light conditions, establishing it as a predictive theoretical framework for the light-induced deformation dynamics of azopolymers. This opens, for the first time, inverse design approaches to azopolymer

surface morphology, where the structured optical field producing a target morphology can be defined and optimized ahead of the experiment.

Central to our implementation is the digital polarization rotator scheme based on an SLM. While the current setup highlights the power and versatility of the approach, further improvements in spatial resolution and angular polarization control using next-generation modulators (e.g., 10-bit SLMs or high-resolution 4K displays) could extend the method to sub-micrometer features. Moreover, the reconfiguration could be scaled to large areas via tiling and motorized positioning, establishing vectorial field-guided lithography as a route to fabricating large-area, multifunctional, surfaces with on-demand anisotropies.

In conclusion, by expanding the role of light from a scalar to a vectorial design parameter, our work introduces a new class of lithography that overcomes intensity-

based photopatterning and establishes fully structured light as a tool for optical lithography and surface engineering. The versatility of our approach makes it compatible with any light modulating devices able to address structured light^{49,50}, such as SLMs and optical metasurfaces. Notably, when the pre-patterned surface is prepared with higher resolution features (e.g., submicron), even the polarization singularities of the engineered structured field could be included as a design parameter in the surface photo-reconfiguration, further extending the set of available optical tools to shape the surface. Potential applications span a wide range of fields, including anisotropic wetting³⁰, directional adhesion⁵¹, surface information encoding⁵², and 3D microstructure-enhanced acoustic streaming⁵³.

Materials and methods

Azopolymer synthesis and fabrication of the micropillar array

The azopolymer used in this study was synthesized by radical polymerization of the photosensitive monomer (E)-2-(4-((4-methoxyphenyl) diazenyl)phenoxy)ethyl acrylate, based on the previously reported procedure³⁰. Reagents were purchased from Merck and used without

further purification. Details of optical absorbance (see also Fig. S1), thermal analysis, and molecular weight distribution have been reported in previous works ($T_g = 67^\circ\text{C}$, $M_w = 27,000\text{ Da}$)^{30,32}. The pre-structured film with micropillar array on the glass substrate was fabricated using a soft lithography technique, as illustrated in Fig. S2. First, a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) soft stamp was fabricated by transferring the surface pattern from a silicone master^{30,38}. This process resulted in a PDMS stamp with a negative surface geometry with respect to the target pattern. A 10 wt% azopolymer solution in 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane was then deposited onto a standard glass microscope coverslip. The prepared PDMS stamp was then gently placed on the azopolymer solution, allowing the azopolymer solution to infiltrate the negative pattern on the stamp. The sample was then left at room temperature for approximately 5 h to allow the solvent in the azopolymer solution to completely evaporate. Finally, the PDMS stamp was carefully removed from the azopolymer surface, leaving the pre-structured azopolymer surface on the glass substrate to be used in the experiment. The azopolymer micropillars were designed from different silica masters, with height, H_o , diameter, D_o , and periodicity, P_o , varied according to the experiment being performed.

Micropillar deformation by homogeneous linearly polarized light

The experimental study of homogeneous linearly polarized light irradiation was performed using an expanded and collimated 488 nm laser (Coherent OBIS 488 LS) with the intensity at the surface plane set to about 0.16 W/cm^2 . The pristine micropillars had a measured height of $H_o \approx 8.4\ \mu\text{m}$, diameter of $D_o \approx 4.0\ \mu\text{m}$, and periodicity of $P_o \approx 10.0\ \mu\text{m}$.

Digital polarization rotator

The optical setup, as shown in Fig. 3b, was based on a Coherent Sapphire 488 LP laser that emits a linearly polarized beam at a wavelength of 488 nm. The beam was expanded by two lenses, with focal length $f_1 = -50\text{ mm}$ and $f_2 = 250\text{ mm}$, respectively. This beam expansion increased the beam diameter to uniformly illuminate the entire active area of the spatial light modulator (SLM). In addition, the lenses were arranged to achieve the desired beam waist and divergence for optimal projection. It is important to note that the lens configuration did not form a strictly afocal system (as the distance between lenses is $d_{21} = 380\text{ mm}$) where the image was formed at infinity. Instead, the lenses were positioned to image the light pattern produced by the polarization rotator at a finite distance. This choice minimized the number of optical components in the setup with respect to a conventional $4f$ scheme, contributing to a more compact and efficient

system. The polarization rotator unit consisted of a reflective SLM (Meadowlark Optics, Inc., phase-only, 1920 pixels by 1152 pixels), located between crossed quarter-waveplates (QWP I and QWP II). The fast axes of QWP I and II were oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$, respectively, to the input beam polarization direction. This combination comprises a variable phase-retarder, rotating the plane of polarization of a linearly polarized input beam by $d\theta$, where $d\theta$ is set by the programmable optical retardation as determined by the gray value addressed to the SLM. The quantitative characterization of the dependence of the output polarization direction on the input gray value addressed to the SLM was performed by positioning a linear polarizer immediately after QWP II. The results, as shown in Fig. S5, indicate a rotation of 1.4° per grayscale increment, demonstrating that 0 to 2π radians of rotation can be imparted by each SLM pixel over 0 to 255 grayscale values.

The spatially structured beam was then projected onto the sample plane by a $40\times$ objective with $NA = 0.65$. The illuminated area corresponded to a demagnified image of the SLM screen with a projected area of approximately $130\ \mu\text{m} \times 78\ \mu\text{m}$. The laser intensity used was $\sim 7.0\ \text{W}/\text{cm}^2$. With this demagnification of the SLM screen, the distance between the pixels on the sample plane was $\sim 0.07\ \mu\text{m}$ (with a density of ~ 15 pixels per μm). This length scale is smaller than the diffraction-limited lateral resolution of the $40\times$, $NA = 0.65$ objective at $488\ \text{nm}$, which is $\approx 0.46\ \mu\text{m}$. Neighboring SLM pixels, therefore, oversample the optical point-spread function and allow us to generate a quasi-continuous polarization pattern $\varphi(x, y)$ that defines the emerging stress pathway.

Micropillar deformation through the digital polarization rotator

For collective pillar reshaping (Fig. 3), an array with measured geometrical parameters $H_o \approx 3.0\ \mu\text{m}$, $D_o \approx 4.0\ \mu\text{m}$, and $P_o \approx 10\ \mu\text{m}$ was used. The individual micropillar deformation experiment (Figs. 4–6) was performed by using an array of azopolymer micropillars with measured geometrical parameters $H_o \approx 3.0\ \mu\text{m}$, $D_o \approx 6.7\ \mu\text{m}$, and $P_o \approx 12\ \mu\text{m}$. To target each micropillar in the array with a $P_o \approx 10\ \mu\text{m}$, a box-shaped polarization map with an area of $10 \times 10\ \mu\text{m}^2$ was used, which corresponds to 148×148 pixels in the grayscale image representing the target polarization map. In case of $P_o \approx 12\ \mu\text{m}$, a box-shaped polarization map with area of $12 \times 12\ \mu\text{m}^2$ was used corresponding to 178×178 pixels in the grayscale polarization design image.

To control the surface plane of the sample in all possible degrees of freedom, a sample holder was placed on an X-Y-Z stage integrated with a gimbal mount. The alignment and the light focusing on a specific region of the azo micropillar array was performed by the motorized stages

and the gimbals, using a bright field imaging system with a CCD camera as visual feedback.

Morphological characterization of microstructures

The morphological characterization of the surface was performed using Scanning Electron Microscopes (Hitachi SU5000 and FEI Nova NanoSEM 450). Prior to image acquisition, the sample underwent a process of metallic coating with a gold layer to increase the conductivity of the surface. The images were obtained using an acceleration voltage of $15\ \text{kV}$ and a high vacuum configuration, which is the standard setting for non-conductive samples with a thin conductive layer on the surface in this SEM. The magnifications used for imaging ranged from $1000\times$ to $9000\times$, depending on the scale of the object of interest.

Modeling of light-induced stress inside the azopolymer-based microvolume

Viscoplastic modeling of topographical structures was carried out using the finite element software ANSYS. Specifically, the Perzyna model was employed to describe the relationship between the rate of plastic strain $\dot{\epsilon}_{pl}$ and the magnitude of light-induced stress τ_0 :

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{pl} = \gamma \left(\frac{\tau_0}{\tau_{yield}} - 1 \right) \quad (3)$$

where τ_{yield} represents the yield stress and the parameter $\gamma = \tau_{yield}/(3\eta)$ defines the viscosity η of the plastic flow. Under constant light intensity, the ratio τ_0/τ_{yield} together with the parameter γ determines the timescale of deformation, but not the final morphology. In the present study, $\tau_{yield} = 5\ \text{MPa}$ was selected based on earlier modeling work⁴³ and calibrated to reproduce the deformation dynamics of the studied azo-polyacrylate, consistent with expectations that photoinduced processes occur at much lower effective yield stresses than in bulk mechanical tests. The parameter $\gamma = 2.5 \times 10^{-3}\ \text{s}^{-1}$ cannot be directly measured but was adjusted for the chosen τ_{yield} to reproduce the experimental timescale of photo-deformation. According to Eq. (3), the dynamic evolution of photo-deformations is governed by the rate of plastic strain $\dot{\epsilon}_{pl}$, which determines the speed of the process. This rate increases with the magnitude of the light-induced stress τ_0 , which scales with the probability of trans-cis photoisomerization of azobenzene chromophores and thus with the incident light intensity, as predicted by theoretical studies¹⁵. Consequently, the dynamics can be accelerated by increasing τ_0 and hence the initial tensile component $\tau_E = 2\tau_0/3$. For Figs. 4, 5, $\tau_E = 25\ \text{MPa}$ was chosen to reproduce the experimentally observed deformation profiles under illumination at $7.0\ \text{W}/\text{cm}^2$. For Fig. 2f and S4, where the simulation time was accelerated by a factor of ten, $\tau_E = 21.5\ \text{MPa}$ was used, corresponding

to an intensity of $\sim 0.16 \text{ W/cm}^2$. The proportionality between τ_0 and the light intensity is expected to hold primarily below $\sim 1 \text{ W/cm}^2$; at higher intensities, the relation becomes nonlinear, and the model should be regarded as an effective approximation.

The model had a cylindrical shape with different boundary conditions. The bottom surface of the sample was 'glued' to the substrate, restricting both rotational and translational movement. In contrast, the upper and side surfaces were left free to deform. To address the computational challenges while maintaining accuracy, a combination of coarse and fine meshing strategies was employed. Critical regions of the cylindrical geometry, such as the top and bottom surfaces where light-induced deformation occurs, were refined using an element size of $0.25 \mu\text{m}$, while less critical areas were discretized with a coarser mesh of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$. The finite element mesh was generated using the ANSYS Meshing module, resulting in structured tetrahedral meshes composed of 6862 elements for Fig. 2 and 8733 elements for Figs. 4, 5, suitable for subsequent finite element analysis.

The light-induced stress tensor was incorporated in ANSYS software using the custom subroutine Userthstrain¹⁷. The thermal strain was chosen in this subroutine using the Perzyna model (3) such that it produced the plastic strain locally prescribed by the light-induced stress. The principal axes of these two tensors coincide. To implement the polarization rotation, each model element was assigned a local coordinate system with the x-axis aligned with the local linear polarization direction and the z-axis normal to the substrate surface. This procedure directly maps the polarization field $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r})$ onto the stress field $\tau(r)$.

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Data availability

Source data are publicly available for this paper on Zenodo.org at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17289199>.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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